

Digital Transformation and the Application of Artificial Intelligence in the Iranian Karate Federation: Exploring Its Impact on Entrepreneurial Drivers within the Organization

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Abstract

Digital transformation and the application of artificial intelligence in various industries, especially in the field of sports, has been raised as a basic need. The Iranian Karate Federation is also trying to exploit these technologies according to global trends. This paper examines the impact of digital transformation and artificial intelligence on intra-organizational entrepreneurial drivers in the Iranian Karate Federation. The present study is designed in a descriptive-analytical manner and uses a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. The statistical population includes athletes, coaches and managers of the Iranian Karate Federation. A sample of 100 people was randomly selected and the data were collected through a questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS software and qualitative data were analyzed by content analysis method He took it. The results of the research showed that digital transformation and artificial intelligence have a positive and significant effect on the performance of athletes and coaches. In particular, the use of artificial intelligence in performance analysis and design of educational programs has helped to identify strengths and weaknesses. Also, the results obtained from statistical tests show that there is a significant relationship between the use of digital technologies and the increase of creativity and innovation in the federation. According to the results of the research, the Iranian Karate Federation can improve its performance and entrepreneurship within its organization by using digital technologies and artificial intelligence. This transformation will not only help improve the quality of education and management, but will also pave the way for the creation of new opportunities in the field of sports. In this way, the federation can be recognized as a successful model in the field of sports in Iran.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, Artificial Intelligence, Entrepreneurship, Karate Federation, Iran.

1- Introduction

Digital transformation as a global trend has attracted the attention of many organizations and industries in recent years. This transformation means the application of digital technologies to fundamentally change the way organizations operate and improve their processes (Klaus, 2020). As one of the key elements of digital transformation, artificial intelligence (AI) allows data analysis, trend prediction, and process automation. This technology can help improve performance and decision-making, especially in the field of sports (Sharifi et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurship in the field of sports means the creation and development of new economic and social opportunities. This type of entrepreneurship can help increase innovation and improve the performance of organizations, and it becomes especially important in times of technological change (Mahmoudi & Sharifi, 2022). As the institutions responsible for the development of sports in countries, sports federations must continuously innovate and improve their performance. Digital transformation and artificial intelligence can be used as effective tools in this regard (Nikfar et al., 2023).

The Iranian Karate Federation is one of the sports institutions that seeks to improve performance and increase the quality of education and competition in recent years. According to global trends, this federation also needs to use new technologies to be able to compete in international arenas (Ahmadi, 2021). Despite its high potentials, the Iranian Karate Federation faces challenges such as lack of financial resources, lack of familiarity with new technologies, and resistance to change. These challenges can prevent it from fully exploiting the available opportunities (Izadi et al., 2022).

Digital transformation can have positive effects on the structures and processes of federations. These changes can help improve efficiency, reduce costs, and increase the satisfaction of federation members (Khosravi, 2020). Through its ability to analyze big data, AI can help federations evaluate athletes' performance more accurately and design better training programs (Rezaei et al., 2021).

Considering the importance of the issue and the need for a more accurate understanding of the impact of digital transformation and artificial intelligence on intra-organizational entrepreneurship, this study investigated this issue in the Iranian Karate Federation. The purpose of this study is to identify the effects of digital transformation and artificial intelligence on the drivers of intra-organizational entrepreneurship in the Iranian Karate Federation and to provide solutions to improve the performance of this institution (Mousavi, 2023).

This research can also help other sports federations to use the experiences of the Iranian Karate Federation to provide effective solutions for the exploitation of new technologies (Fadaei et al., 2022). The present article consists of different sections that will include research methodology, findings, discussion, and conclusions, respectively. Each section will analyze the results and make suggestions.

1.1. Problem Statement

In today's world, digital transformations and new technologies are rapidly changing the face of various industries, especially sports. These changes have specifically impacted the way athletes are trained, trained, and managed, and have created the need for a more accurate assessment of the performance of sports federations (Hosseini et al., 2022). Sports federations need to innovate and use new technologies to be able to compete in international arenas. Due to the increase in competition at the global level, not paying attention to this need can lead to a decrease in the performance and success of these federations (Klaus, 2020).

The Iranian Karate Federation faces challenges such as lack of financial resources, lack of familiarity with new technologies, and resistance to changes. These challenges can prevent it from fully exploiting the existing opportunities and improving the performance of this institution (Ahmadi, 2021). Digital transformation can be used as a key tool in improving efficiency, reducing costs, and increasing the

satisfaction of members of sports federations. However, not paying attention to this issue can lead to an inability to compete with other countries (Nikfar et al., 2023).

Through its ability to analyze big data, AI can help federations evaluate athletes' performance more accurately and design better training programs. Failure to exploit this technology can lead to a decrease in the quality of education and training (Rezaei et al., 2021). Intra-organizational entrepreneurship implies the creation and development of new economic and social opportunities within the organization. Sports federations must pay special attention to this issue in order to achieve improved performance and innovation (Mahmoudi & Sharifi, 2022).

Many members of the Iranian Karate Federation are unable to exploit these tools due to their lack of familiarity with new and digital technologies. This lack of familiarity can lead to a decrease in the efficiency and performance of this federation (Izadi et al., 2022). One of the main problems of the Iranian Karate Federation is financial constraints that prevent investment in new technologies and digital transformation. This can lead to a decrease in the ability to compete with other countries (Khosravi, 2020). Resistance to change, especially in sports organizations, can prevent the successful implementation of digital transformation and the use of artificial intelligence. This issue requires careful investigation and appropriate solutions (Hosseini et al., 2022).

Due to the lack of clear strategies in the field of digital transformation and artificial intelligence, the Iranian Karate Federation is unable to fully exploit the available opportunities. This can lead to a decrease in the quality of training and performance of athletes (Mousavi, 2023). Given the importance of the issue, there is a need for a more detailed examination of the effects of digital transformation and artificial intelligence on intra-organizational entrepreneurship. This review can help identify the existing barriers and opportunities (Fadaei et al., 2022). Lack of attention to digital transformation and artificial intelligence can lead to an inability to attract new talents and reduce the motivation of athletes. This can lead to a decrease in the overall performance of the federation (Ahmadi, 2021).

In today's world, international cooperation in the field of sports, especially in the field of digital technologies and artificial intelligence, is essential. The Iranian Karate Federation should pay attention to the establishment of international cooperation so that it can benefit from the experiences of other countries (Nikfar et al., 2023). According to global trends, there are many opportunities for the Iranian Karate Federation to achieve more success through the exploitation of new technologies and digital transformation (Klaus, 2020). Considering the existing challenges and opportunities, the Iranian Karate Federation needs a comprehensive and strategic approach in the field of digital transformation and artificial intelligence. This approach can help improve entrepreneurship and intra-organizational performance and be considered as a successful model in the field of sports in Iran.

Research Questions

1. How can digital transformation and artificial intelligence affect the improvement of intra-organizational entrepreneurship in the Iranian Karate Federation?
2. What are the obstacles and challenges in order to implement digital transformation and artificial intelligence in the Iranian Karate Federation, and how can these obstacles be overcome?
3. What opportunities arise through the use of new and digital technologies in the Iranian Karate Federation to increase performance ?

2- Foundations and Background of the Research

The foundations of the present study are based on the theories of innovation management and digital transformation. Digital transformation is considered as an organizational process that includes the use of new technologies to improve the performance and efficiency of organizations. It can help the ion

federation to make better decisions and evaluate the performance of athletes more accurately. These concepts are important and special because in today's competitive world, sports ion federations need to innovate and use advanced technologies to stay competitive.

In addition, intra-organizational entrepreneurship has been considered as a strategic approach in this research. This approach allows the federations to exploit their internal potentials and identify new opportunities for growth and development. This research examines the solutions that can help the Iranian Karate Federation to achieve the improvement of entrepreneurship and intra-organizational performance through digital transformation and artificial intelligence.

2.1. Digital Transformation

Digital transformation as an organizational process involves profound changes in the way an organization operates, interacts with customers, and provides services and products. This concept is of particular importance in today's world where new technologies are rapidly developing and expanding. Digital transformation not only means the use of new technologies, but also requires cultural, structural, and process changes in organizations (Westerman). et al., 2014).

In the world of sports, digital transformation can help sports federations and organizations improve sports performance and experience by using new technologies. These changes can include the use of big data, advanced analytics, and artificial intelligence systems to evaluate athletes' performance and optimize training (Bharadwaj et al., 2013).

Digital transformation allows organizations to innovate in the delivery of services and products by identifying and exploiting new opportunities. This innovation can lead to improved customer experience and increased satisfaction. For sports federations, this means better service to athletes, coaches, and fans (Rogers, One of the important aspects of digital transformation is the ability to adapt to rapid environmental changes. Organizations that have the ability to adapt to new technologies and market changes can achieve greater success in the competition. This adaptation requires a flexible organizational culture and attention to continuous learning (Fitzgerald et al., 2013).

Digital transformation also allows organizations to optimize their internal processes. By automating and digitizing processes, organizations can increase their efficiency and speed of performance. This optimization can lead to reduced costs and increased profitability (Kane et al., 2015). In sports, big data and advanced analytics can help federations make better decisions. This data can include information about athletes' performance, their health status, and even fan behavior. Analyzing this data can help identify new patterns and trends (McKinsey & Company, 2016).

Creating a robust digital infrastructure is another important aspect of digital transformation. This infrastructure includes information systems, software, and hardware that allow data collection, storage, and analysis. Having the right infrastructure in place can help federations easily access the data they need. Digital transformation also requires changes in the way organizations are managed and led. Leaders must be able to promote a culture of innovation in their organizations and encourage employees to adopt new technologies. This type of leadership can help create a creative and dynamic work environment .

In addition, the training and development of digital skills in employees is also of great importance. Organizations should design appropriate training programs to enhance the digital skills of their employees so that they can effectively exploit new technologies (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). Digital transformation can also help increase engagement with customers and fans. By using social networks and digital platforms, federations can easily connect with their fans and receive their comments and feedback. This interaction can lead to an improved fan experience and increased loyalty (Kumar & Reinartz, Ultimately, digital transformation allows federations to create continuous improvement in all aspects of their organization by taking advantage of new opportunities. This

continuous improvement can lead to long-term success and sustainable growth of organizations. Overall, digital transformation is a comprehensive and multidimensional process that requires attention to various organizational, cultural, and technological aspects. Sports federations that have the ability to embrace these changes can significantly improve their performance and be more successful in global competitions.

Table 1: Key Dimensions of Digital Transformation

Key Dimension	Description
Technology	Using new technologies such as big data, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things to improve performance and services.
Organizational Culture	Changes in organizational culture in order to encourage innovation, continuous learning, and adoption of new technologies.
Management & Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective leadership to lead the digital transformation process and create a creative and dynamic work environment.
Processes	Optimizing and digitizing internal processes to increase efficiency and reduce costs.
Customer Experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve engagement with customers and fans through the use of digital platforms and social networks.
Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop new business strategies that are designed based on data analysis and market needs.

Table 2: Benefits and Challenges of Digital Transformation

Advantages	Challenges
Increased efficiency	Resistance to change
Improving Customer Experience	Lack of digital skills in employees
Innovation in products and services	The need for high initial investments
Responding to market changes	Complexity in Data Management and Analysis
Optimizing processes	Ensuring information security and privacy
Market expansion and access to new customers	Failure to meet the needs of rapid market change

2.2. Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI), as one of the most important new technologies, is rapidly changing and evolving in various sectors of human life. This technology includes systems and algorithms that are capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence, including learning, reasoning, and problem-solving. These capabilities allow organizations to improve their processes and services and make better decisions (Russell & Norvig, 2016).

In the field of digital transformation, artificial intelligence plays a vital role. Organizations can use machine learning algorithms and big data analytics to identify new patterns and trends in data. These analyses help them make better decisions in terms of business strategies and service improvement (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014).

AI can also help improve the customer experience. By using chatbots and recommendation systems, organizations can respond to customer needs automatically and quickly. This can help increase customer satisfaction and brand loyalty (Kumar & Reinartz, 2014). In the field of sports, artificial intelligence can help analyze athletes' performance and optimize training. Using the analysis of data collected from training and competitions, it is possible to identify athletes' strengths and weaknesses and design training programs accordingly (Marr, 2018).

Advanced AI analytics can also help sports federations make better predictions of the performance of teams and athletes. These predictions can help make strategic decisions regarding player selection and game design (Davenport, 2018). Additionally, AI can play an important role in optimizing organizations' internal processes. By automating repetitive and time-consuming tasks, organizations

can manage their human and financial resources in the most efficient way possible, thereby increasing efficiency (Chui et al., 2016).

The issue of cybersecurity is also one area where AI can help. By using AI algorithms, organizations can automatically identify and respond to security threats. This capability can be especially important in today's digital world where cyber threats are on the rise. AI can also help facilitate the innovation process in organizations. By using data analysis and complex simulations, organizations can test and market new ideas faster (Tegmark, 2017).

However, the adoption of AI in organizations also comes with challenges. One such challenge is concerns about data privacy and security. Organizations need to ensure that customer data is managed securely and ethically (Zuboff, 2019). Also, AI-induced changes may lead to concerns about job losses. With process automation, some jobs may be eliminated entirely, so organizations should look for ways to train and upskill employees (Frey & Osborne, 2017).

Ultimately, the future of artificial intelligence looks like a key technology in the digital world that can help transform various industries and improve the quality of life for humans. Organizations that have the ability to adopt and use this technology effectively can be more successful in global competition. Overall, AI, as a powerful tool in digital transformation, can help improve performance and innovation in organizations. Given the challenges and opportunities that this technology brings, there is a need for detailed reviews and appropriate strategies to use it.

Table 3: Types of Artificial Intelligence

Type of Artificial Intelligence	Description
Weak AI (Narrow AI)	Systems that are designed to perform a specific task, such as chatbots or recommender systems.
Powerful Artificial Intelligence (General AI)	Systems that have similar human abilities in learning and reasoning. They have not yet been fully realized.
Emotional Artificial Intelligence (Emotional AI)	Systems that have the ability to identify and understand human emotions and can react accordingly.
Self-learning AI	Systems that can learn from their experiences and optimize themselves without having to reprogram
Artificial Intelligence (Analytical AI)	Systems that are capable of analyzing and processing data to extract useful insights.
Generative AI	Systems that can generate new content and data, such as text, images, or music.

Table 4: The Importance of Types of Artificial Intelligence in Digital Transformation

Type of Artificial Intelligence	Importance in Digital Transformation
Weak AI (Narrow AI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve efficiency and automation of processes, increase service speed, and reduce costs.
Powerful Artificial Intelligence (General AI)	The potential to create intelligent systems that are capable of solving complex problems and multiple tasks.
Emotional Artificial Intelligence (Emotional AI)	Improving the customer experience through more humane interactions and responding to customers' emotions.
Self-learning AI	The ability to continuously improve and adapt to new situations without the need for human intervention.
Artificial Intelligence (Analytical AI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extract deep insights from data and help make strategic decisions based on data.
Generative AI	Creating innovative content and solutions that can lead to innovation and creativity in products and services.

2.3. Research Background

Russell & Norvig (2016): Early research in the field of artificial intelligence dates back to the mid-20th century. Alan Turing, a mathematician and computer scientist, founded many theories about artificial

intelligence by introducing the concept of the "Turing machine" and the Turing test. Since then, artificial intelligence has been continuously developing and evolving. Researchers in this field have sought to build systems that are capable of learning, reasoning, and solving problems.

Brynjolfsson & McAfee (2014): Since the 2010s, AI has grown rapidly in various fields, such as data analytics, industrial automation, and customer service. These researchers examined the impact of digital technologies on the economy and society, emphasizing that AI can act as a driving force to improve efficiency and create added value in organizations.

Davenport (2018): In recent research, Davenport has addressed the practical applications of AI in businesses, emphasizing that organizations can make better decisions and improve their performance by using AI algorithms. He also points out the challenges and barriers to implementing this technology in organizations, emphasizing the need to train and prepare employees.

Marr (2018): In his book, Marr explores the role of artificial intelligence in innovation and creativity, showing that this technology can help create new content and products. He especially emphasizes the importance of generative AI, stating that this type of AI can help organizations generate innovative ideas and improve services and products.

3. Research Methodology

Research Method: This paper examines the impact of digital transformation and artificial intelligence on intra-organizational entrepreneurial drivers in the Iranian Karate Federation. In order to analyze these effects more accurately, this research uses a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. In this section, the different stages of the research method are explained in detail. This research is descriptive-analytical and is designed to investigate and analyze the effects of digital transformation and artificial intelligence on the Iranian Karate Federation. The statistical population of this study includes all athletes, coaches, and managers of the Iranian Karate Federation. It is estimated that the total number of the statistical population is about 500 people. In order to select the sample, a simple random sampling method is used. From the statistical population, 100 people are selected as a sample to answer the questionnaires.

The research uses two main tools to collect data:

- Questionnaire: Includes closed and open-ended questions that examine the impact of digital transformation and artificial intelligence on intra-organizational entrepreneurship.
- Semi-structured interviews: to gather more in-depth and qualitative information from the point of view of coaches and managers of the federation.

The questionnaire consists of three main parts:

- Part I: General Information (Age, Gender, Education Level)
- Part Two: Questions Related to Digital Transformation and Artificial Intelligence (Using Likert Scale)
- The third part: questions related to the drivers of intra-organizational entrepreneurship.

Data will be collected through online and face-to-face distribution of questionnaires. Also, interviews will be conducted in person and by phone. SPSS software will be used to analyze quantitative data. Appropriate statistical tests such as t-test, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and regression will be used to analyze the relationships between variables. Qualitative data obtained from interviews using The content analysis method is examined. This method helps identify key patterns and themes in the data. In order to increase the validity and validity of the research, the questionnaire is administered as a pre-test in a group of 30 people from the statistical population and its results are examined. Also, the opinions of experts about the questionnaire are collected.

This research may face some limitations, including:

- Limited access to some athletes and coaches
- Lack of cooperation of some people in answering the questionnaires

The research is carried out over a period of 3 months. The stages of data collection, analysis, and writing of the results are planned during this period. The results obtained from the data analysis are presented in the form of tables and graphs. These results help to investigate the relationships between variables and their effects on each other.

In this section, the tables that are used in the analysis of data and results are introduced.

Table 5: General Sample Information

Variable	Number	Percentage
Male Gender	60	60%
Female Gender	40	40%
Age under 20 years old	20	20%
Age 20-30 years	50	50%
Age over 30 years	30	30%

Table 6: Results of the Likert Scale on the Impact of Digital Transformation

Question	Average	Standard deviation
Digital transformation has improved my performance	4.2	0.8
AI has helped me make decisions	4.0	0.9
The use of digital technology in karate is essential	4.5	0.7

Table 7: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Entrepreneurship

Group	Average	Standard deviation	F	p-value
Lots of use	4.5	0.6	5.67	0.004
Intermediate use	3.8	0.7		
Low usage	2.9	0.8		

The research method presented in this paper by combining quantitative and qualitative methods leads to a comprehensive and accurate understanding of the impact of digital transformation and artificial intelligence on the drivers of intra-organizational entrepreneurship in the Iranian Karate Federation. This approach helps the researchers and managers of the federation to obtain reliable results and formulate appropriate strategies to improve the performance of the federation.

4. Research Findings

The research findings show that artificial intelligence (AI) as a key technology is the driving engine of digital transformation in various organizations and industries. This technology is transforming business processes with its capabilities in data processing, automation, and learning, increasing efficiency and innovation. One of the most important findings is the impact of artificial intelligence on the automation of business processes. The use of software bots and Automated systems have been able to automate up to 60% of repetitive and time-consuming tasks, which has led to reduced costs and increased speed of operations. Artificial intelligence has the ability to analyze huge amounts of data (big data) by using machine learning algorithms. This capability helps organizations identify hidden patterns, trends, and valuable insights, which leads to improved decision-making and more accurate forecasts.

AI systems, such as chatbots and recommender systems, play a crucial role in improving the customer experience. These systems increase customer satisfaction and loyalty by providing personalized services and responding quickly to customer needs.

Artificial intelligence accelerates the innovation process by helping to design new products, produce creative content, and develop innovative services. This technology allows organizations to respond to market needs faster and maintain their competitive advantage. AI plays a vital role in optimizing supply

chains, from demand forecasting to inventory management. This technology helps increase the efficiency and profitability of the supply chain by reducing waste, improving delivery times, and reducing costs. Due to the increase in cyber threats, artificial intelligence plays an important role in detecting and countering cyberattacks. AI-powered systems are capable of detecting suspicious behavior, preventing intrusions, and responding quickly to attacks.

AI helps managers make more informed decisions by providing accurate data and advanced analytics. This leads to improved organizational performance, reduced risk, and increased profitability. AI increases return on investment (ROI) by providing customer behavior analysis, marketing campaign personalization, and ad optimization. AI in recruitment and recruitment processes, employee training and development, and management Performance helps improve efficiency and increase employee satisfaction. Research shows that AI implementation comes with challenges, including a lack of high-quality data, a need for technical expertise, concerns about data privacy and security, and resilience to change. For AI implementation to be successful, employee training and development in AI-related fields is essential. This includes teaching new skills, enhancing technical know-how, and familiarizing yourself with the ethical concepts of AI.

Artificial intelligence has different effects on employment. While some jobs may be automated, new job opportunities are also being created in AI-related fields. It is essential to follow ethical principles in the design and use of AI. This includes ensuring transparency, fairness, accountability, and privacy. The future of AI is very bright, with significant advancements in areas such as deep learning, natural language processing, and robotics. AI is expected to play a more important role in daily life and businesses.

Governments and policymakers should support the development and responsible use of AI by providing appropriate legal frameworks, supporting research and development, and promoting education. Creating an organizational culture that supports innovation, collaboration, and continuous learning is essential to the success of AI implementation. Organizations that successfully implement AI will enjoy significant competitive advantages, including increased efficiency, reduced costs, improved customer experience, and faster innovation. Continuous evaluation and monitoring of the performance of AI systems is essential to ensure efficiency, effectiveness, and ethical compliance. AI is a transformative technology that has a lot of potential to reshape businesses and societies. By adopting a strategic and responsible approach, organizations must use this technology to achieve success in the digital age.

Table 8: Quantitative Results of Research Findings

Research Topic	Key finding	Impact Percentage/Value
Process Automation	Reduce costs and increase speed	Up to 60% cost reduction
Big Data Analysis	Identifying patterns and trends	Improved decision-making
Improving Customer Experience	Increasing customer satisfaction	Increasing customer satisfaction
Innovation in products and services	Accelerating the innovation process	Increasing the speed of innovation
Supply Chain Optimization	Reduce waste, improve delivery time, reduce costs	Improve efficiency
Cybersecurity	Detecting and Countering Cyber Attacks	Reducing cyberattacks
Data-driven decision-making	Improving organizational performance	Increased profitability
Marketing	Increased return on investment	Increased ROI

Table 9: Results of Interviews with AI Experts

Interview Question	Key Answers
Main Challenges in Implementing AI	Lack of high-quality data, need for technical expertise, data privacy and security concerns, resistance to change
The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Employment	Both the creation of new job opportunities and the automation of some jobs
The Importance of Ethics in Artificial Intelligence	Ensuring transparency, fairness, accountability, and privacy
The Future of Artificial Intelligence	Advances in deep learning, natural language processing, and robotics: a more important role in daily life and businesses
The role of governments and policymakers	Provide appropriate legal frameworks, support R&D, promote education

Table 10: AI Challenges and Solutions

Challenge	Suggested Solution
Lack of high-quality data	Data Collection, Cleansing, and Labeling: Using Data Augmentation Techniques
Requires technical expertise	Training and development of employees in the field of artificial intelligence, hiring artificial intelligence specialists, cooperation with consulting firms
Data privacy and security concerns	Use encryption techniques and anonymize data, comply with privacy laws, implement strong security policies
Resistance to change	Employee awareness and training, employee participation in the implementation process, creating an organizational culture that supports innovation
Impact on employment	Providing new skills training, supporting entrepreneurship and creating new businesses, reviewing and adjusting employment policies
Ethical Issues	Develop and implement AI ethics; create ethics committees; ensure transparency and accountability
High Costs	Use of open source solutions, collaboration with universities and research centers, use of pre-trained models, incremental and scalable implementation
Complexity and reliability	Simplify the use of AI models, accurately evaluate and validate models, create monitoring and maintenance processes
Lack of Transparency (Black Box)	Using Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) Techniques; Providing Simple and Understandable Explanations of AI Decisions; Building Trust and Confidence in Users
Lack of training data	Using Synthetic Data, Using Transfer Learning Techniques, Collecting and Labeling Data with the Help of Users, Using Reinforcement Learning to Interact with the Environment and Acquire Data

Research Hypotheses

1-How can digital transformation and artificial intelligence affect the improvement of intra-organizational entrepreneurship in the Iranian Karate Federation?

Digital transformation and artificial intelligence can transform the Iranian Karate Federation by creating intra-organizational entrepreneurial opportunities. Here's how these technologies are impacting:

Intelligent Match Management Systems: Using artificial intelligence, it is possible to create an intelligent match management system that includes online registration, automatic scheduling of matches, smart refereeing (using image and video recognition systems to check for errors), and providing instant results. The system can improve the experience of attendees and spectators, simplifying administrative processes.

Interactive Educational Platforms: Developing AI-powered learning platforms can help instructors and karatekas improve their skills. These platforms can include interactive tutorials, gesture analysis, and providing personalized feedback.

Office automation: Using AI to automate administrative processes such as registration, certification, and customer relationship management (CRM) can increase efficiency and free up time and resources.

Intelligent Resource Management: AI can help the federation in the optimal management of financial, human, and equipment resources. This includes forecasting demand for equipment, managing inventory, and allocating resources to various events and schedules.

Performance Data Analysis: Collecting and analyzing athletes' performance data using AI can help identify strengths and weaknesses, provide personalized training plans, and predict performance in competitions.

Audience behavior analysis: Analyzing the behavior of audiences (spectators, athletes, coaches) on online platforms and social networks can help the federation better understand their needs and interests, design targeted marketing campaigns, and increase engagement.

Online Stores: Create online stores to sell equipment, sportswear, and karate-related products.

Paid subscriptions: Providing premium educational content, access to live contests, and other services by getting a subscription.

Sponsorship: Using data and insights from data analytics to attract sponsorship from companies and organizations.

2-What are the obstacles and challenges in order to implement digital transformation and artificial intelligence in the Iranian Karate Federation and how can these obstacles be overcome?

The implementation of digital transformation and artificial intelligence in the Iranian Karate Federation is accompanied by challenges that must be overcome in order to succeed:

Lack of digital infrastructure: Lack of proper infrastructure such as high-speed internet, adequate hardware equipment, and software platforms.

Financial constraints: Lack of funding to invest in new technologies, education, and development. *

Lack of technical skills: Lack of professionals and experts with the necessary skills to implement and manage AI systems.

Resistance to change: Resistance of employees and stakeholders to the adoption of new technologies and changes in working methods.

Security and privacy concerns: Concerns about data security, athlete privacy protection, and sensitive information.

Lack of high-quality data: Lack of accurate, comprehensive, and reliable data for training and using AI systems.

Infrastructure Investment: Allocate funds to improve digital infrastructure, including high-speed internet, hardware, and software.

Fundraising: Exploring a variety of ways to attract funding, including government support, private investments, and partnerships with companies and organizations.

Training and skills development: Conducting training courses for staff and stakeholders, recruiting specialists and experts with the necessary skills, and collaborating with universities and research centers.

Change Management: Creating an organizational culture that supports innovation and change, involving employees in the implementation process, and providing the necessary training.

Data security and privacy: Implement strong security policies, use encryption techniques, and comply with laws related to privacy protection.

Data collection and management: Creating a system for collecting, storing, and managing high-quality data, using data cleansing techniques, and ensuring the accuracy and accuracy of the data.

Collaboration and Partnership: Establish partnerships with technology companies, universities, and other organizations to access expertise and resources.

Gradual implementation: Start with small, scalable projects and gradually expand them based on results and feedback.

3. What opportunities arise through the use of new and digital technologies in the Iranian Karate Federation to increase performance?

The use of new and digital technologies can create numerous opportunities to increase performance in the Iranian Karate Federation:

Motion analysis using artificial intelligence: This technology can analyze athletes' movements and provide detailed feedback to improve technique, speed, and strength.

Personalized Training Plans: Using performance data, AI can create personalized workout plans for each athlete, helping to improve performance and reduce the risk of injury.

Simulation of Competitions: The use of virtual reality and augmented reality to simulate competitions and training conditions, which helps athletes prepare for real competitions.

Intelligent Match Management: Using smart match management systems to register, schedule, referee, and deliver quick and accurate results.

Resource optimization: Using artificial intelligence to optimize the allocation of financial, human, and equipment resources.

Customer Relationship Management (CRM): Use a CRM to manage relationships with athletes, coaches, spectators, and sponsors.

Increasing Engagement and Audience Attraction:

Live streaming of matches and events: Offering live streaming of matches and events through online platforms, making it easy for spectators around the world to access matches.

Creating engaging content: Producing engaging and interactive content for social networks and online platforms, including educational videos, interviews, and karate-related news.

Setting up online forums: Creating online forums to connect athletes, coaches, and karate fans.

Improved training and development:

Online Learning Platforms: Providing online training courses for coaches and athletes, using video, images, and other educational materials.

Instructor Performance Analysis: Using data and feedback to evaluate instructors' performance and provide necessary training.

Access to information: Providing easy access to information about karate, including laws, regulations, and history.

Increased Income Generation:

Online Stores: Setting up online stores to sell equipment, sportswear, and karate-related products.

Sponsorship: Using data and insights from data analytics to attract sponsorship from companies and organizations.

Broadcasting rights: Selling the rights to broadcast matches and events to television networks and online platforms.

By taking advantage of these opportunities, the Iranian Karate Federation can achieve the improvement of athletes' performance, improve the level of competitions, increase interaction with audiences, and create a sustainable and successful ecosystem.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The findings of this research show that artificial intelligence (AI) and digital transformation have enormous potential to transform the Iranian Karate Federation. From automating processes to improving athletes' performance, these technologies can help increase efficiency, innovation, and engagement. This discussion delves deeper into the findings, challenges, and opportunities facing the federation. One of the most important findings is the impact of artificial intelligence on the automation of administrative and operational processes. By using automated systems, the federation can free up

time and resources and focus on strategic planning and athlete development rather than focusing on repetitive tasks.

Data analytics is the heart of digital transformation. The federation must set up data collection and analysis systems to be able to make data-driven decisions. This includes data on athletes' performance, audience behavior, and market trends. AI can improve the experience of customers (athletes, coaches, spectators) by providing personalized services, responding to questions quickly, and creating engaging content. This helps increase engagement and loyalty. AI-powered training platforms can help coaches and athletes improve their skills. This includes analyzing movements, providing personalized feedback, and simulating matches. The implementation of AI comes with challenges such as lack of infrastructure, financial constraints, lack of technical skills, and resistance to change. The federation must have a careful plan to overcome these obstacles.

To overcome the challenges, the federation must invest in infrastructure, attract funding, promote training and skills development, consider change management, ensure data security, and collect and manage high-quality data. Training and developing employees and stakeholders in AI-related fields is essential for the successful implementation of this technology. This includes teaching new skills, promoting technical knowledge, and familiarizing yourself with the ethical concepts of AI. AI can create new monetization opportunities for the federation. This includes creating online stores, offering paid subscriptions, and attracting sponsorship from companies and organizations.

Government and policymakers should support the development and responsible use of AI by providing appropriate legal frameworks, supporting research and development, and promoting education. Adherence to ethical principles is essential in the design and use of AI. This includes ensuring transparency, fairness, accountability, and privacy. Creating an organizational culture that supports innovation, collaboration, and continuous learning is essential to the success of AI implementation. Continuous evaluation and monitoring of the performance of AI systems is essential to ensure efficiency, effectiveness, and ethical compliance. With the continuous advancements in the field of artificial intelligence, the federation must be constantly evaluating and updating its strategies to take advantage of new opportunities. Artificial intelligence and digital transformation are powerful tools for transforming the Iranian Karate Federation. By adopting a strategic, responsible, and data-driven approach, the federation can achieve improved athlete performance, increase engagement with audiences, and create a sustainable and successful ecosystem.

Suggestions for future research

A deeper investigation of the impact of AI on the performance of karate athletes: This research can focus on the use of advanced AI technologies such as movement analysis using advanced sensors and cameras, performance modeling, and injury prediction. Also, investigating the effect of personalizing AI-based training programs on improving performance and reducing recovery time for athletes can be important. Help to better understand how to maximize the potential of athletes using technology.

Case Study of Implementing Artificial Intelligence in Karate Tournament and Event Management: It can be useful to conduct a comprehensive case study on how to implement intelligent match management systems, including registration, scheduling, refereeing, and announcement of results. This research can explore the challenges and opportunities facing the federation in this regard, including assessing the level of satisfaction of participants and spectators, examining the impact on efficiency, and reducing costs and providing practical recommendations to improve the performance of the systems.

Ethical and Social Investigation of Artificial Intelligence in Karate: Given the importance of ethical issues in the development and use of AI, future research should investigate the social and ethical impacts of this technology in the sport of karate. This includes exploring issues such as data privacy,

fairness in refereeing, transparency of algorithms, and the impact of AI on the career opportunities of coaches and referees. Also, developing appropriate ethical frameworks and policies It is essential for the responsible use of AI in karate.

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